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Deliverable 4.1

Templates for data ingestion and service development

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Executive Summary

ARCFISH will develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic. The DTO will be based on the existing Blue Insight platform that supports the market segments of the ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022). The New Blue Economy, also known as the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE), is a concept that promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries focusing on achieving long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities is the key to uphold good living conditions for its residents. However, the negative impacts of traditional economic activities such as overfishing, marine pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change have threatened the health and sustainability of the ocean, leading to declining fish stocks, loss of biodiversity, and increased coastal vulnerability to natural disasters. New data products and services, co-developed with relevant stakeholders, are needed to provide a better basis for decision-making in fisheries planning and management. For example, for Disko Bay, western Greenland, ecosystem indices based on an improved ecosystem model could include monthly spatial maps of zooplankton biomass and production, benthos biomass, shrimp biomass, and upwelling areas. Data collected around Iceland towards the Barents Sea onboard fishing vessels and in seafood processing could be implemented in the DTO to support relevant stakeholders. For the Arctic in general, potential new services could include advanced eLogbooks and spatiotemporal pattern detection and visualisation. For cost-efficiency these services must leverage novel digital technologies such as DTOs to acquire, process, analyse and visualise heterogeneous data from a wide range of sources.

This document will provide an overview of the system, outline the supported data types and formats, and detail the expectations for services and methods that will be incorporated into the digital twin.

More information on the project can be found at: <https://www.arcfish.eu>.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma Separated Value
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
eLOG	Electronic Logbook (Trackwell)
ERS	Electronic Reporting System (Trackwell)
FLUX	Fisheries Language for Universal Exchange
GEBCO	General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans
GeoJSON	Geographic JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)
GeoTIFF	Geographic Tag Image File Format
GGA	Generalized Gradient Approximation
GIS	Geographic Information System
GLL	Geographic Position - Latitude/Longitude
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NMEA	National Marine Electronics Association
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RMC	Recommended Minimum Specific GNSS Data
SBE	Sustainable Blue Economy
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SSD	Solid-State Drive
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
UTM	Universal Transform Mercator
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System (Trackwell)
WAV	Waveform Audio File Format
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service

1. Introduction

The aim of the ARCFISH project is to develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic. The DTO will be based on the existing Blue Insight platform that supports the market segments of the ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022). The New Blue Economy, also known as the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE), is a concept that *promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits*. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries focusing on achieving long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities is the key to uphold good living conditions for its residents.

Figure 1. The ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022)

This document will provide an overview of the system, outline the supported data types and formats, and detail the expectations for services needs and methods that will be incorporated into the digital twin.

2. Data ingestion

To create an overview of the available stakeholder data, and the available and sharable data services we will create several templates. The templates will describe the data available, the data formats, the relevant metadata and any usage limitations or licenses.

To be able to link the data into a Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), all datatypes must have a relation to both time and space, either by a precise coordinate and timestamp, or a bounding box and time-range.

Any metadata to provide contextual information is also important to improve the value of the DTO beyond the operations of a Geographic Information System (GIS) and must be provided in the templates provided.

We have pre-selected several relevant datatypes for the system to limit the initial implementation. The datatypes list is by no mean exhaustive but will serve as guidance for the data providers. It is also selected based on the availability of data onboard the fishing vessels part of the project.

We will also propose a format for importing data services, the primary operations of data services will be converting a datatype, for instance shape to GeoJSON or provide an API to offer filter or aggregate data services to others.

2.1. Selected Datatypes

The DTO is prioritizing standardization with regards to spatial data types. The standards chosen is the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards of Web Map Services, Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF and Maps API. This does not mean that datatypes outside the standard is not acceptable, but it means that if a project participant want to offer those data types (for instance shape files or .dxf files), they will be required to offer or point to a data conversion service.

2.1.1. Spatial data

We expect bathymetric data to be delivered following the quality metrics defined by GEBCO, the prioritized data format is the floating point GeoTIFF file format and in particular the Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF as outlined by OGC. We will standardize on WGS84, and projections in Web Mercator or UTM will be desired. The data provided must be unrestricted with regards to national security concerns.

Vector data, such as boundaries, exclusion zones, marine sanctuaries, economic zones can be added to the system using the GeoJSON format as implemented by OGC.

Existing models for context in the DTO, obtained through WMS/WFS following OGC standard layers, can be proposed as supporting information (such as GEBCO, BarentsWatch, etc.). The system will also provide a WMS server for hosting of models produced in the project.

2.1.2. External Timeseries

External timeseries can be ingested into the database system, the system has native support for three different formats. GeoJSON,, NetCDF (selected types) and CSV. Other formats can also be ingested, but then a data conversion service need to be offered. In the case of GeoJSON, the standard used for the properties need to be described in the metadata, and in case of CSV the headers need to be described. Expected external timeseries include, mammal movements, biomass estimates, ARGO floats movements, Earthquakes and AIS tracks. All time should be reported as UTC time. The DTO solution is moving towards ingesting OGCs EDR standard for timeseries as well, and the plan is to add this standard towards the end of the development period.

2.1.3. Vessel data

Vessel navigation can be ingested using the external timeseries format, however, to add simplification from the fishing vessels with SIMRAD equipment, we will create an onboard conversion system, Blue Insight Datalogger, that will integrate relevant NMEA messages and handle the conversion and upload to the DTO timeseries storage. Relevant vessel sentences include GGA, GLL and RMC data.

Other relevant Fisheries vessel data can also be integrated as vessel data, including sources like the data provided in the project from the Trackwell systems. Data from eLog, an electronic logbook for on-board

catch registrations, the vessel monitoring system (VMS), and the Electronic Reporting System (ERS) will be ingested on the Fisheries Language for Universal Exchange (FLUX) format.

2.1.4. Meteorological

Meteorological data can be ingested using the external timeseries format, however, to add simplification from the vessels with Vaisala equipment, we will create an onboard serial data conversion system, Blue Insight Datalogger, that will integrate relevant meteorological messages. This includes datatypes like temperature, pressure and humidity.

2.1.5. Oceanographic

Oceanographic data can be ingested using the external timeseries format, however, to add simplification and standardization, the priority is to read this on NetCDF format. Data regarding Salinity, Temperature and Ocean currents are the prioritized data types.

2.1.6. Hydrophone

Passive hydrophone data can be ingested into the system in its native WAV format. Processed hydrophone data can also be ingested in the external timeseries formats (mammal observations, earthquakes, etc), metadata for processed hydrophone data should contain the processing components utilized, the version and a link to the original raw data.

2.1.7. Echosounder

The ingestion of echosounder data will provide useful information about abundance of biomass (fish and plankton) in an area. We suggest 3 different ways of supplying echosounder data.

1. SIMRAD RAW format from the ES80 or EK80 echosounders
2. Biomass at a given ocean level and position reported in the GeoJSON format (either point or linestring), if the data needs to be decimated, we suggest a biomass average over a nautical mile, the native biomass calculation from the ES or EKs can be used.
3. An array of backscatter reflections, normalized to 500 measurements pr ping.

2.1.8. Sonar

The sonars can produce data in the format of echosounders. But the newest SIMRAD sonars can also provide additional information about the size and biomass of a tracked school of fish. In the project we will create ingestion surfaces for this format.

The SIMRAD sonars delivers the PSIMMDS NMEA format describing the position, time, size, biomass and speed of the school. We will integrate this into the DTO.

3. Data ingestion template

The data ingestion template consists of 3 major elements:

3.1. Datatype description

The datatype describes what format the data is, in accordance with the descriptions outlined in the datatype chapter. It can either be placed in a separate README.MD file together with the data, or provided manually.

3.2. Data delivery mechanics

Most of the data integrated in the DTO will arrive as data files. The system offers several ways of integrating data, with a priority on direct uploads to its storage infrastructure, currently hosted in Azure Cloud. Several applications can be used to upload including the Azure Storage Explorer, azcopy scripts provided on request by Kongsberg Discovery or the built in SFTP solution. In addition, Kongsberg Discovery will supply a native running datalogger application that can integrate with local data and upload these.

3.3. Metadata description

Metadata template must be included and submitted with the dataset, following the standard outlined by the Metadata template for ARCFISH. If consistent updates are planned it is sufficient to send metadata the first time, and then every time they might change.

As the number of data sources are expected to be limited within ARCFISH, we will review the template and descriptions in workshop meetings. If the number of sources should turn out to be beyond the possibility for manual handling, we will integrate a solution into a data upload portal.

4. Service ingestion template

In addition to have the capability of ingesting data, the system shall also provide the support of 3rd party data services. This ensures a more flexible and reusable platform. Furthermore, it will ensure that work performed to process a datatype will not be limited to use within Blue Insight, but will also be reusable in other digital infrastructures.

To adjust the scope in the ARCFISH project we will differentiate between two major types of services:

- Data processing service
- Data access service

4.1. Data processing services

The data processing service will convert one data format to another data format. In the ARCFISH project we will not differentiate on the type of operation the service does. Normal data processing tasks include decimation, normalization, format conversion, classification among many other. An example of a data processing task can be fish school detection. The input data will then be a folder of "RAW" files, available in a storage location within the digital infrastructure. The data processing service can be an AI service, looking for fish schools. The output data would be a GeoJSON array, with properties including confidence, estimated biomass, model used, version of model.

Figure 2. The elements in a generic data processing service.

For the project we expect that all data processing services are packaged into a docker container, and that the docker container are provided by a docker file, a compressed library (a Tarball) or a link to an accessible artifactory in for instance Docker Hub or Zenodo.

We also need an estimate on the resources consumed by the data processing service, with focus on memory, CPU and specialized hardware requirements like GPUs or SSD drives.

If several process steps are needed, Kongsberg provide a Task Orchestrator Framework application to combine multiple data processors.

4.2. Data access services

The data access services will create a specialized view from a dataset. This could be a special aggregation of multiple datasets into a data package, or a specialized filter.

Figure 3. The elements in a generic data access service.

The application programming interface (API) provides a machine-readable data integration point while the graphical user interface (GUI) provides a human readable interface, like a web page.

The distribution of data presentation services will be the same as the data processing services. In the event of multiple containers utilized, a “docker compose” file must be added to communicate the connection between the different containers.

5. Conclusions

The ARCFISH project aims to develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) to support sustainable Arctic fisheries. Based on the Blue Insight platform, the DTO will back the New Blue Economy's efforts for sustainable ocean resource conservation. This initiative is vital for the long-term sustainability and resilience of Arctic ecosystems and communities, promoting better living conditions for residents.

The project addresses the negative impacts of traditional economic activities such as overfishing, marine pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change, which have threatened the health and sustainability of the ocean. By co-developing new data products and services with relevant stakeholders, ARCFISH aims to provide a better basis for decision-making in fisheries planning and management. Potential new services include advanced eLogbooks, spatiotemporal pattern detection, and visualization.

This template description describes the ingestion of data and services to the DTO and emphasizes the importance of standardizing spatial data types and prioritizing common data formats such as GeoTIFF, GeoJSON, and NetCDF. The description highlights the need for metadata to provide contextual information and improve the value of the DTO beyond GIS tool operation. By leveraging novel digital technologies, ARCFISH aims to acquire, process, analyze, and visualize heterogeneous data from various sources, ultimately supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic.

6. References

Heslop et al., 2022. GOOS / MTS / NOAA DIALOGUES WITH INDUSTRY Background paper V1.

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